

ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL AND SEMANTIC TRANSFORMATIONS IN POETRY TRANSLATION

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the lexical and semantic transformations used in the process of poetic translation, one of the most common types of translation among young people who love literary literature today. In addition, the article examines how poems are translated from one language to another and what methods are used to translate them. Various manuals and a collection of translated poems are taken as a source for the article.

Keywords: lexical transformation, semantic transformation, linguaculture, generalization, method of word addition.

SHE'RIY TARJIMADA LEKSIK VA SEMANTIK TRANSFORMATSIYALAR TAHLILI ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola tarjimaning bugungi kunda badiiy adaabiyotni sevib o`quvchi yoshlar orasida keng tarqalgan turlaridan biri she`riy tarjima jarayonida foydalaniladigan leksik va semantik transformatsiyalarni analiz qiladi. Undan tashqari, maqolada she`rlar qanday bir tildan boshqa tilgaa o`girilishi va unda qanday usullardan foydalangan holda tarjima qilinishi ham ko`rib chiqiladi. Maqola uchun manba sifatida turli xil qo`llanmalar va tarjima qilingan she`rlar to`plami olingan.

Kalit so`zlar: leksik transformatsiyalar, semantik transformatsiyalar, lingvomadaniyat, umumlashtirish, so`z qo`shish metodi.

АНАЛИЗ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИХ И СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕОБРАЗОВАНИЙ ПРИ ПЕРЕВОДЕ ПОЭЗИИ АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируются лексико-семантические трансформации, используемые в процессе поэтического перевода, одного из наиболее распространенных сегодня видов перевода среди молодежи, любящей литературную литературу. Кроме того, в статье рассматривается, как

переводятся стихотворения с одного языка на другой и какие методы используются для их перевода. В качестве источника для статьи были взяты различные пособия и сборник переводных стихотворений.

Ключевые слова: лексические трансформации, семантические трансформации, лингвокультура, обобщение, способ сложения слов.

INTRODUCTION

Since the 70s of the 20th century, the process of translation from English, German, and French into Uzbek has begun. One of our poets, Jamal Kamal from English, Abdulla Sher from German, and Shavkat Rahman from Spanish, studied the original language and tried to translate the works directly from the original. By the end of the 20th century, the number of translators who decided to directly translate from Uzbek into foreign languages expanded. Detailed information about the main principles of translation theory can be found in candidate and doctoral works on translation theory, especially poetic translation, from the period of independence to the present day. Although poetic translation differs from prose translation in many ways, there are some commonalities between them. They serve interlingual poetic or poetic communication. Information in a poetic text is fundamentally different from information in a prose text. The content of information in the poem can be different, contradict each other. Poetic information includes factual and conceptual, that is, information related to meaning. They are closely related to each other and at the same time they are dynamically opposed to each other. Factual and substantive information provides information about the external real or unreal world based on specific facts and events. The translation of the poetic text, which is part of the artistic speech, takes into account the rules of the structure of the poem. Rhythm, tone, syntactic structure, artistic image and other artistic elements used in the analysis of prose are in focus. The concepts and terms mentioned above are also used in the analysis of the poetic text, but they are implemented on the basis of the rhyming rules of poetry. Each time, the translator tried to study the experiences of poetic translation, identify the achievements and shortcomings of the poetic translation, and develop some recommendations based on the results of the analysis of the poetic translation. The most important task of poetic translation is to try not to turn a good poem into a bad poem in translation, to preserve the content of the translation as completely as possible, to preserve both the weight and the tone of the

poetic text forms in accordance with the poem's content. Not only the translator, but also the reader should feel the good or bad of the translation in one reading.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Lexical transformation involves replacing words or phrases in the source text with equivalent expressions in the target language. Grammatical transformations involve adjusting the grammatical structure of sentences in the source text to better fit the target language's rules.

The semantic transformation methodology enables data sources to be transformed into a target common data model by only providing abstract mapping rules and eliminates the effort spent to address database specific details.

Poetry translation: poem by Robert Burns "A fond kiss"

Who shall say that fortune grieves him,
While the star of hope she leave him
Me, nae cheerful twinkle lights me,
Dark despair around benights me.

Begoyim Xolbekova's translation: "So`nggi bo`sa"

Taqdir ekan ne ham qildik biz,
Umidni chin baxt deb bilibmiz.
Ammo bugun ko`zlarimda yosh,
Yorsiz yo`lim yoritmas quyosh.

As can be seen from this poetic translation, skillful word selection was used in the translation process. This poem is not translated literally, but it has many lexical and semantic transformations. For example, to give an example of lexical transformation, the word choice sentence "*the star of hope*" when translated literally translates as "*umid yulduzi*", but the word of lexical transformation in the poem addition method is used. In addition, we can also find a semantic transformation in this poetic translation. For example, almost all sentences are translated using the generalized method of semantic transformation. For example, "Me, nae cheerful twinkle lights me" – "*Ammo bugun ko`zlarimda yosh*" like that.

CONCLUSION

Translation of traditional poems is complicated and involves a number of problems. In this case, it is necessary to take into account not only the weight, cadence, rhyme, tone, harmony of the poem, but also the type and characteristics of the poem in

different combinations, as well as the individual style of the author, as well as the characteristics of the poem in each language. The translator of this poem has in-depth knowledge, traditions of two languages, national characteristics, linguistic and cultural aspects, the main idea, image, stylistic means and methods in the poem, and participated in expressive delivery of poetic information to the reader. It is necessary to take into account the function of each of the language elements, the characteristics of the period in which the poem was written.

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